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From Contested Territories to alternatives of development: Learning from Latin America

Deliverable 5.3:

Working Paper 3

Systematizing research findings with regard to participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

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Deliverable 5.3:**Working Paper 3 Systematizing research findings with regard to participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory**

1. DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET
2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY
3. FOREWORD
4. SECTION 1: SYSTEMATIZATION OF CONTRIBUTIONS IN CRITICAL AND DECOLONIAL SOCIAL THEORIES
 - 4.1 INTRODUCTION
 - 4.2 ALTERNATIVE SOCIOECONOMIC PRACTICES AND RATIONALITIES IN THE FACE OF CONCENTRATION: SOCIAL, SOLIDARITY, AND POPULAR ECONOMIES
 - 4.3 USE, APPROPRIATION, AND REGULATION OF NATURE
 - 4.4 LAND CONFLICTS AND DISPUTES
 - 4.5 STATE POLICIES IN TERRITORIAL ACCUMULATION
 - 4.6 BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES
5. SECTION 2: PARTICIPATORY MECHANISMS AND COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE MECHANISMS
 - 5.1 INTRODUCTION
 - 5.2 WHY IS IT IMPORTANT TO DEVELOP PARTICIPATORY AND COLLABORATIVE MECHANISMS?
 - 5.3 PARTICIPATORY MECHANISMS ARE NOT NEUTRAL
 - 5.4 FROM PARTICIPATION TO COLLABORATION: COLLABORATIVE MECHANISMS FOR KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE
 - 5.4.1 DIGITAL PARTICIPATION PLATFORMS
 - 5.4.2 PARTICIPATORY AND KNOWLEDGE CO-PRODUCTION PROCESSES CARRIED OUT BY THE NETWORK
 - *COMMUNITY WORKSHOPS*
 - *MULTI-STAKEHOLDER MEETINGS AND DIALOGUES*
 - *SOCIAL CARTOGRAPHIES AND COUNTER-CARTOGRAPHIES*
 - *BEYOND TEXT: SENSORY METHODOLOGIES*
 - *CRITICAL TERRITORIAL FIELD-WALKS*
 - *CITIZEN SCIENCE AND COLLABORATIVE SURVEYS*
 - *UNIVERSITY EXTENSION PROGRAMMES*
 - 5.5 DISCUSSION AND CONTRIBUTIONS
 - 5.6 BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

1. DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This working paper systematizes the theoretical and methodological contributions of the Contested Territories Network regarding participatory mechanisms, collaborative knowledge exchange, and decolonial social theory. It examines how capitalism, grounded in processes of territorial accumulation, has produced structural inequalities that persist through colonial and neo-colonial dynamics, and how alternative epistemologies and participatory approaches offer pathways toward more just and situated forms of knowledge. The paper contributes conceptual and methodological tools to advance decolonial, participatory, and context-sensitive approaches to social research and territorial transformation.
Keywords	Decolonial social theory, participatory mechanisms, co-production of knowledge, territorial accumulation, otros saberes

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Contested Territories Network set out to advance a political ontology of territorial struggles by building innovative knowledge that places dispute and alternative knowledge at the center of its understanding of territories. This Deliverable 5.3, an expression of Work Package 5 on *Otros saberes*, links Task 5.1, which visualizes decolonial approaches and *otros saberes* that illustrate alternative knowledge and local organizational practices as a basis for the production of transformative knowledge; Task 5.2, which accounts for community workshops for reflection, analysis, and co-production of knowledge, as well as other forms of participation and knowledge exchange; and, specifically, it fulfills Task 5.3, which involves reflecting on the mechanisms and content of decolonial theory and methodology through ethical, methodological, and theoretical debates on decolonial practice.

This working paper systematizes the theoretical and methodological contributions of the Contested Territories Network regarding participatory mechanisms, collaborative knowledge exchange, and decolonial social theory. It examines how capitalism, grounded in processes of territorial accumulation, has produced structural inequalities that persist through colonial and neo-colonial dynamics, and how alternative epistemologies and participatory approaches offer pathways toward more just and situated forms of knowledge. The paper integrates theoretical, methodological, and empirical analysis through four thematic areas – alternative economies, nature, land, and state policies– while systematizing participatory practices such as workshops, mapping, and multi-actor dialogues. These are understood as interconnected political and epistemic devices that link research, action, and advocacy. The findings highlight both the transformative potential of knowledge co-production, and its persistent challenges related to power, governance, and sustainability.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

3. FOREWORD

Capitalism, as the dominant system for organizing life in economic and productive terms, has grounded its power in processes of territorial accumulation, deployed unequally across different regions of the world. This uneven development has produced a global order in which central countries dominate trade relations, social and cultural aspirations, and political models, while developing countries are integrated in a peripheral and subordinate way. Within this hegemonic configuration, reproduced through a homogenizing model further intensified by the effects of globalization, alternative ways of living, understanding territory, constructing knowledge, and producing goods have been rendered invisible and subordinated.

The modern positivist paradigm, built by the dominant powers, has privileged quantification and the search for abstract regularities over attention to historical contexts and cultural particularities. In doing so, it has left out multiple forms of exploitation, dispossession, and subordination that persist in territories marked by historical colonialism and contemporary neocolonialism. In response, the social sciences and humanities have recognized the need to recover critical and decolonial theoretical perspectives in order to interpret processes of accumulation. Decolonial criticism highlights the importance of the power of the world's epistemic diversity and the coexistence of multiple ways of knowing. In this context, the “epistemologies of the South” (De Sousa Santos, 2010) emerge from experiences of resistance to the global order and from the collective construction of alternatives in subalternized territories.

This epistemological shift is also methodological, prioritizing participatory, dialogical, and situated modes of inquiry. Over recent decades, the application and analysis of participatory mechanisms and collaborative processes of knowledge exchange have become central to the social sciences. From early proposals such as Participatory Action Research (PAR) to more contemporary approaches to knowledge co-production, these traditions seek to overcome the conventional extractivist research model and replace it with more inclusive, holistic, and contextually situated research practices (Fals Borda, 2001; Norström et al., 2020). These methodologies respond, on the one hand, to the need to generate relevant knowledge in the face of the complex challenges presented by our social, environmental, and political reality, but they also seek to raise ethical questions about the asymmetrical power relations between academia and other forms of knowledge.

Thus, the first part of this working paper revisits theoretical-methodological perspectives, reflections, and debates arising from case studies developed within the framework of the Contested Territories Network. This section is organized around four thematic areas: (a) alternative economies, (b) disputes over the use, regulation, and appropriation of nature, (c) struggles over land and (d) the state and public policies, which illustrate how conventional theoretical and methodological perspectives (positivist, Eurocentric, etc.) can be problematized and reconfigured through alternative approaches. From an approach that emphasizes the importance of contextualization and the complexity of analytical processes by recovering the perspectives of local actors, tensions are highlighted as a subject of

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

analysis, enabling new questions and alternative ways of addressing the dynamics of accumulation in different territories.

The second part systematizes and critically analyses a set of participatory and collaborative devices deployed by the Contested Territories Network and their contributions to the theory and practice of participatory research from a decolonial standpoint, providing lessons that transcend the specificity of each device. The analysis underscores that these mechanisms are not merely methodological tools; they are political and epistemic practices that reconfigure relationships between academia, communities, and social actors. They demonstrate that participation functions not as a single method, but as an ecology of interconnected devices that weave together encounter, research, and action.

The analysis underscores the importance of generating useful and immediately applicable outputs: workshop-action-feedback cycles have influenced community, political, and academic agendas through maps, guides, memory archives, audiovisual productions, and toolboxes. The experiences of Contested Territories confirm that co-production deepens when it recognizes epistemic plurality (local, ancestral, experiential, somatic knowledge) and legitimizes non-textual forms of representation. They also reaffirm that effective feedback and context-specific co-production strengthen the political relevance of knowledge produced “from below”.

However, while the analysis of the mechanisms described shows significant contributions in epistemic, methodological, political, and organizational terms; it also identifies enduring challenges that expose the limits and dilemmas faced by many participatory and co-production processes: persistent asymmetries of power, representation, and language (how to redistribute power in unequal contexts); issues of knowledge governance, reciprocity, and ownership (how to protect shared knowledge); and questions of temporality and sustainability (how to maintain fragile collaborations over time).

Ultimately, this working paper seeks to contribute to ongoing debates on how knowledge is produced, validated, and mobilized across territories marked by inequality and contestation. By drawing on the experiences of the Contested Territories Network, it aspires not only to document participatory practices but to foreground their transformative potential. The reflections that follow invite readers to rethink collaboration as both an epistemic and political practice, capable of unsettling inherited hierarchies and opening pathways toward more plural, situated, and just ways of knowing and inhabiting the world.

4. SECTION 1: SYSTEMATIZATION OF CONTRIBUTIONS IN CRITICAL AND DECOLONIAL SOCIAL THEORIES

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4.1 Introduction

Historically, capitalism as the dominant system for organizing life in economic and productive terms has built its foundations upon processes of territorial accumulation, unevenly deployed across different regions of the world. This expansion has created a global landscape in which core countries have dominated trade relations, social and cultural aspirations, and hegemonic political models –thereby conditioning the integration of developing countries through their peripheral and subordinate inclusion in the global order.

These processes –capital accumulation and resource domination on one side, dispossession of common goods (both material and symbolic) on the other– are grounded in the tension between use value and exchange value (Marx, 2008). From a critical perspective, in the contemporary order the elementary form of wealth is expressed through the commodity, which embodies the struggle between these dimensions of value, the labor that produces it, and the territorial disputes over its control (Santin, 2025).

The historical struggle over production, domination, and spatial appropriation (Lefebvre, 1973) has guided processes of capital accumulation. The contest over the territorial organization of wealth represents the form taken by the broader struggle for control of the commodity –produced within the tension between use value and exchange value (García Linera, 31/08/2021). The homogenizing tendency of capital, together with the effects of globalization, has led to processes of invisibilization and subalternization of alternative ways of living, building territories, and producing goods to meet collective needs.

In relation to the different ways of understanding, addressing, legislating, and responding to this debate, the State, the Market, and Civil Society –each with their own uneven, contradictory, and conflictive synthesis in every region– have shaped distinct forms of capital organization. These have resulted in “economic-productive, technological, political, and cultural systems that sustain and legitimize a specific territorial order” (Santin, 2025, p. 176).

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

Territorial disputes over the control of production, distribution, and consumption processes bring forth multiple debates concerning the scales involved (national and global), the productive agents prioritized, the underlying logics, the models of development promoted, the epistemological and methodological frameworks that provide them with coherence, and the alternative or resistant approaches that challenge them.

In recent decades, analyses of territorial accumulation processes at the global scale have increasingly questioned the interpretative and epistemological limits of the modern-positivist paradigm. The tradition of thought rooted in European Modernity, with its universalist claims, has tended to homogenize the diversity of historical, economic, and cultural experiences that shape the contemporary world. This vision –marked by the ideas of linear progress, economic development, and the expansion of instrumental rationality– has proven insufficient to account for the specific forms of accumulation that emerge in the Global South and in the so-called “peripheries” of the Global North (Quijano, 2000; Mignolo, 2005).

Positivist approaches have privileged quantification and the search for abstract regularities over attention to historical contexts and cultural particularities. As a result, they have contributed to obscuring the multiple forms of exploitation, dispossession, and subordination that permeate accumulation processes in territories marked by historical colonialism and contemporary neocolonialism. The reduction of social complexity to standardized and supposedly neutral categories reinforces a Eurocentric gaze that constrains the understanding of phenomena such as extractive accumulation, dependent financialization, the marginalization of community and popular economies, and the diverse ways of using, appropriating, and/or exchanging natural goods (De Sousa Santos, 2010).

In response to these limitations, the social and human sciences have increasingly embraced the need to recover critical and decolonial theoretical perspectives capable of rethinking the epistemological foundations from which accumulation processes are interpreted. These perspectives challenge the modern/colonial matrix of knowledge and seek to transcend the dualisms between center and periphery, between “developed” and “backward,” revealing how such categories are part of the geopolitics of knowledge that reproduces relations of power and domination (Quijano, 2000; Mignolo, 2005).

Decolonial critique highlights the importance of recognizing the world’s epistemic diversity. Authors such as De Sousa Santos (2010) have emphasized the need to understand the historical “epistemicide” through which indigenous, peasant, and popular knowledges were marginalized or destroyed. Recovering decolonial perspectives therefore entails creating space for “epistemologies of the South” –forms of knowledge that emerge from experiences of resistance and community-building in subalternized territories. This involves not only an epistemological shift –by questioning the supposed neutrality and universality of modern knowledge– but also a methodological one, by fostering participatory, dialogical, and situated modes of inquiry.

From a theoretical standpoint, these traditions offer valuable tools for understanding the specificities of accumulation processes in the Global South. Concepts such as Harvey’s (2003) “accumulation by dispossession” or Gudynas’s (2009) notion of “extractivism” help explain how the expansion of capitalist logic operates through violent or unequal appropriation of resources, bodies, and territories. Moreover, fruitful dialogues can be

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

established between these perspectives and the structuralist theories of development formulated in the 1950s and 1960s within the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America, as well as their later elaborations in Latin American dependency theory (Cardoso & Faletto, 1969; Marini, 1973). These earlier approaches already emphasized the need to explain accumulation dynamics from a peripheral standpoint, in opposition to linear frameworks of development.

Building on the contributions of critical and decolonial theories to the understanding of accumulation processes at different scales, this section aims to recover theoretical-methodological perspectives, reflections, and debates emerging from case studies developed within the *Contested Territories Network*. The text is organized around four thematic areas –(a) alternative economies, (b) disputes over the use, regulation, and appropriation of nature, (c) land struggles, and (d) the state and public policies– which synthesize key issues identified in these studies.

Rather than providing definitive answers or methodological prescriptions, the goal is to highlight tensions and perspectives that, from critical and decolonial approaches, open new questions and suggest alternative ways of engaging with the dynamics of accumulation across territories. The selection of these thematic areas seeks to illustrate how conventional (positivist, Eurocentric, etc.) theoretical-methodological perspectives can be problematized and how alternative frameworks can be constructed. These approaches are committed to contextualization and to understanding the complexity of analytical processes, recovering the perspectives of local actors to inspire future research on emerging issues.

4.2 Alternative Socioeconomic Practices and Rationalities in the Face of Concentration: Social, Solidarity, and Popular Economies

Antonella Santin (CEUR- CONICET)

4.2.1 Introduction

In a context of global crisis characterized by asymmetric power relations between core and peripheral countries, global inequality parameters manifest in multiple ways –through the uneven integration of each nation into the world-system (Wallerstein, 2004) and its development models, as well as through disparities in living conditions and the levels of well-being of their populations. These global asymmetries take concrete shape in the rising cost of living and production, the decline in consumption, the stagnation of workers' incomes, and the persistent difficulties in accessing employment, food, healthcare, education, and basic services, among others.

The socio-economic concentration of production, tied to capital accumulation and the appropriation of rents derived from the access and management of basic goods and services, forms the foundation of the current scenario. Marked by profound social, economic, technological, and climatic transformations, the evolving capital-labor relationship, the ways in which wealth is produced and distributed, and the ensuing territorial disputes (Santin, 2025) lie at the heart of the problem.

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

Given these challenges, there is an urgent need to revisit the competing socioeconomic rationalities that underpin the theoretical, political, and organizational models guiding contemporary relations of exchange and the everyday reproduction of life. From a critical and decolonial perspective, drawing on the contributions of Cielo, Gago, and Tassi (2023) and Rivera Cusicanqui (2018), this section aims to recover the potential of social, solidarity, and popular economies (hereafter SSPE) as both a theoretical-political perspective and an evolving field of contestation (Sterling Plazas & Rosa, 2025). These experiences stand in opposition to the dominant and conventional model of production, commercialization, and consumption of goods and services guided by an economic rationality centered on capital accumulation.

Accordingly, this section first explores the competing socioeconomic models in order to examine the features and potential of SSPE. It then synthesizes the main theoretical, methodological, and epistemological contributions emerging from the *Contested Territories Network* concerning these alternative socioeconomic approaches. Finally, it concludes with a brief reflection.

4.2.2 Competing Models: Between Economic Rationality and the Expanded Reproduction of Life

The neoclassical school of economic thought, as the main theoretical foundation of capitalism, posits that human nature is inherently individualistic, competitive, and indifferent to others, driven by the goal of maximizing profit (Rosa, 2016). Since Western modernity, the abstract notion of labor –closely tied to capital concentration– has produced historical forms of alienation, displacement, and sustained expropriation of value (Rivera Cusicanqui, 2018). On these grounds, the processes of original and colonial accumulation have been exalted, reinforcing the figure of the *homo economicus* as a timeless and placeless subject, detached from history and culture, who extends himself homogeneously across territories.

In contrast, both in the Global North and South, living economic practices have given rise to socioeconomic relations of exchange that –empirically and historically– emerged in Europe from the 1980s onward (Rosa, 2016), and in Latin America during the height of neoliberal projects (1990-2000). These dynamics gave rise to what are now known as social, solidarity, and popular economies. Such practices emerged both as survival strategies and as efforts toward political transformation, seeking to meet fundamental human needs.

These empirically grounded initiatives, situated within their distinct socio-historical, cultural, and geographical contexts, reveal regional divergences, since “exchange as market (that is, as a system of equivalences normalized by capital and internationalized as *habitus*) only became hegemonic a few centuries ago, and in the peripheries of the world system it unfolds discontinuously, in systoles and diastoles –moments of articulation and fragmentation” (Rivera Cusicanqui, 2018, p. 45). In Europe, community and transformative economies emerged as organizational and cooperative forms aimed at fostering more egalitarian relations of production and exchange –particularly of goods such as food– based on values of justice, equity, and sustainability, with social transformation as their central goal. In contrast, in the Global South, the persistence of semi-colonial practices, subordinate integration, and recurrent economic crises have generated a diverse map of alternative experiences in urban, rural, and peri-urban areas that combine “knowledge and practices

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

enabling social reproduction in territories deeply marked by neoliberal dispossession, while simultaneously reinventing and connecting forms of conflictivity and concrete livelihood capacity” (Cielo et al., 2023, p. 36).

Despite their differences, these regional experiences share key features that demonstrate the strength of such socioeconomic alternatives. From a critical perspective, Cielo, Gago, and Tassi (2023) identify four defining and empowering characteristics of SSPE:

1. **Creative production in the face of dispossession:** Social groups generate and regenerate “productive realities, material dynamics, and organizational forms” (Cielo et al., 2023, p. 35), placing the value of life at the center and asserting agency to ensure social reproduction.
2. **Political subject formation:** The actors driving these economies mobilize knowledge, tools, organizational trajectories, and histories, constituting themselves as political subjects who produce emancipatory alternatives.
3. **Temporal sustainability:** These economies endure because they arise from the very processes lived by organized social actors, weaving complex temporalities that transcend moments of social, economic, or political crisis, persisting as modes of social and economic resistance.
4. **Strategic centrality:** They are increasingly central and strategic, expanding in scale and scope as more people excluded from formal labor markets participate in them.

This potential is reflected in the following data. The social and solidarity economy represents 7% of global GDP and employment, generating 8% of the EU's GDP through 2.8 million cooperatives, mutuals, and associations, which together create 13.6 million jobs across agriculture, industry, services, and construction (Fundación Espíritu, 20/01/2025). In Spain, according to the *Confederación Empresarial Española de la Economía Social* (CEPES), the social economy accounts for 10% of GDP and 12.5% of total employment –above the global average.

In Latin America and the Caribbean, fragmented public policies (Deux Marzi, 2023) and limited institutional measurement tools make it difficult to quantify participation and assess the socioeconomic impact of these productive sectors. For example, in Brazil, as of 2006 there were 21,859 solidarity economic enterprises (SENAES, 2006), involving about 10% of the population organized into cooperatives, associations, informal groups, and other structures (Espelt & Azevedo, 2018). In Argentina, in 2019 there were 11,627 formal entities –mutuals and cooperatives– with nearly 28 million associated members (INAES, 2019).

Both formal and informal associative forms embody a wealth of experience, knowledge, and tools that demonstrate the potential, viability, and real impact that promoting, supporting,

and institutionalizing these economies can have –at both small and large scales– on social, economic, and territorial development.

4.2.3 The Contested Territories Network and Socioeconomic Rationalities in Dispute

To systematize some of the main findings and analytical approaches produced by the Contested Territories Network concerning alternative social and economic practices to market hegemonies, this section compiles key concepts and empirical realities mobilized within the project that have sharpened the diagnosis of territorial disputes and illuminated the analytical and practical relevance of these alternatives.

From a theoretical standpoint, the network’s work highlights the analytical categories used to examine territorial accumulation. The model of territorial accumulation grounded in Western modernity and market rationality reveals how capital encroaches upon the reproduction of life, social relations, common goods, and territories –appropriating both paid and unpaid labor (Mies, 1986; Federici, 2010; Castro et al., 2022). This logic disproportionately affects women, racialized groups, and Indigenous peoples. Displacement and dispossession as conditions for others’ accumulation (Harvey, 2004; Castro et al., 2022) have been constant features since the system’s origins. In this way, the capitalist separation between production and the reproduction of life (Moore, 2020; Castro et al., 2022) legitimizes plunder and reinforces the division between the sociopolitical and economic spheres –an enduring feature of mercantile, liberal, and orthodox models of economic organization.

Analytically, this framework provides a useful lens for conceptualizing SSPE as a broad theoretical and epistemological umbrella grounded in a critical territorial perspective. Processes such as the commodification and touristification of food systems, the displacement of traditional populations, and land-use conflicts all directly or indirectly stem from these broader logics.

Empirically, research within the network has focused on experiences of food production, marketing, and consumption. Centering the practices of actors and public policy responses, theoretical and methodological approaches have been developed to analyze socio-territorial processes and popular market circuits (Calegaris et al., 2023). The cases studied –ranging from the commodification of traditional markets in the UK amid policy gaps, to their revaluation and gentrification in Madrid, to the centralization of fresh-food trade in Buenos Aires– illustrate the unequal territorialization of socioeconomic processes and the emergence of viable alternatives to them. Among these are short food supply chains and agroecological markets, which promote decentralized trade, community-based regulation, and equitable food access.

At the core of these experiences lie diverse labor forms, socio-community organizations, and state-civil collaborations marked by asymmetrical power relations. In some cases, conventional market logics prevail, prioritizing profit over redistribution. In others, grassroots initiatives have achieved degrees of institutionalization and positioned themselves as viable alternatives to concentrated food systems, emphasizing social reproduction, solidarity-based labor, and the right to food.

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

A notable case is the *Mercado de San Fernando* in Lavapiés, Madrid (Grad, 2025). Conceived as a socio-economic space where actors, practices, and meanings coexist and contest one another, this municipal market –home to local shops, large distributors, and gourmet businesses– reflects the coexistence of multiple logics within the same urban space. Neoliberal transformations promoting gourmetization and privatization –backed by local policy– encounter “alternative practices that highlight the agency of self-organized consumers in shaping production-marketing-consumption circuits” (Grad, 2025).

These markets, understood as *territories in dispute* (Grad, 2025), host “flexible and grassroots practices of food distribution and decentralized trade among subaltern sectors (...) which have helped avert food crises in the face of limited state capacity” (GT Economías Populares - CLACSO, 2020; Cielo et al., 2023, p. 14). Through these logics, commercial activity can be redefined –transforming it from a mechanism of wealth accumulation into an *urban common good* (cf. Laval & Dardot, 2015; Hardt & Negri, 2009; Grad, 2025). These practices thus act as forms of resistance to exclusionary models (Rosa, 2016), centering the reproduction of popular classes and revitalizing local trade and food supply, reaffirming food as a human right and community organization as a key dimension of economic life.

4.2.4 Conclusions

In the United Nations’ *International Year of Cooperatives*, the promotion and implementation of institutional actions aimed at social justice, decent work, and sustainable development (ILO, 09/2025) find in SSPE a crucial epistemological, theoretical, practical, and political perspective for our times. These initiatives offer a concrete means of decolonizing understandings and narratives of socioeconomic processes beyond the oppressor’s values (Rivera Cusicanqui, 2010), recognizing the transformative impact of popular, situated, and integral practices, and affirming their capacity to overcome the primacy of capital in favor of labor (Quijano, 2014) and the sustenance of life.

In light of new global trends, conventional economic logics –based on homogenization and the monopoly structures built by concentrated capital– are proving increasingly inadequate. It is therefore urgent to pay attention to the specific socio-territorial processes that emerge daily from grassroots responses to successive crises around the world. Such recognition requires, in turn, several key commitments: acknowledging the protagonists of SSPE as political subjects; developing decolonial theoretical and methodological approaches that center them; fostering multi-actor collaborations; institutionalizing territorialized socioeconomic initiatives; revising local and national legislative agendas; reaffirming the State’s central role as regulator and redistributor of social value; and building a shared agenda that prioritizes social needs and the pursuit of dignified living conditions for all citizens.

4.3 Use, appropriation, and regulation of nature

Lautaro Alba (CEUR-CONICET)

4.3.1 Introduction

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

In the current context of the eco-social crisis –where the effects of biodiversity loss, deforestation, soil desertification, changes in average temperatures, extreme droughts, and floods are evident– it is essential to deepen our understanding of the relationship between human and non-human nature. Following the Network's theoretical approach, it is not possible to study this issue without taking into account that nature is, and has been, central to the process of building capitalism, where both its appropriation and that of human labor have played key roles in the transition from a feudal to a capitalist economy, as Karl Marx explains based on the concept of primitive accumulation (Castro et al., 2022). This not only involved the construction of a particular economic model, but also, through the persecution and elimination of pre-existing forms of production, the separation of peasants from their land, and new forms of appropriation of nature, led to the construction of a new nature: external and usable. However, as Jason Moore (2020) explains, the ecological crisis is not something external to capitalism, but rather an internal crisis resulting from this historical production of nature.

In this context, the aim of this section is to identify and analyze cases presented within the framework of the Network, where the relationship between human and non-human nature comes into tension due to different logics of use, regulation, and appropriation in the territories from a decolonial perspective. Working from this perspective will help us find the most useful analytical tools for understanding this phenomenon, while trying to avoid reproducing classic dualisms such as Society-Nature.

4.3.2 Case studies and approaches in the Contested Territories Network

This subsection examines seven cases published in other works by the Network (available at: Kanai et al., 2022; Lukas et al., 2025) that address phenomena linked to territorial accumulation in different parts of Latin America and Europe. To deepen the analysis, they were grouped into three categories: popular habitat management, neoliberalization of nature, and processes of resistance. This grouping does not imply that the works have been approached from identical theoretical frameworks or that they have been dedicated to investigating the particular issue of disputes over the use and appropriation of nature, but rather responds to a need specific to this section to bring together works with similar approaches and shed light on new dimensions that emerge from the joint analysis.

4.3.2.a The first set of cases addresses popular habitat management at the intersection with the production of new realities in the face of the vestiges of capitalist production systems that modify environmental variables that impair the ability to inhabit the territory.

The first case is that of the neighbourhoods located on the banks of the Las Piedras and San Francisco streams (Almirante Brown and Quilmes, Buenos Aires, Argentina) presented by Jorge Blanco, Ricardo Apaolaza, and Juan Pablo Venturini (available at: Kanai et al., 2022). The residents of these neighbourhoods, in collaboration with representatives from academia, government, and international cooperation agencies, began to develop projects to improve the socio-ecological conditions of the territories where they live, specifically where a landfill used to be located. The project envisages the community-led construction of a public park, with the aim not only of improving access to quality sports and leisure opportunities, but also as a mechanism to increase the surface area for absorbing excess rainwater, which is another problem in the area. In view of this situation, they are also

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

designing an early flood warning mechanism that alerts community organizations in the basin, allowing for a reduction in the risks posed by incidents caused by excess water.

The second case is that of the territorial conflict in Alto Milluni (El Alto, Bolivia) presented by Carlos Revilla (available at: Lukas et al., 2025). This territory, traditionally inhabited by indigenous communities, has historically been disputed by mining and other extractive projects and, more recently, by the real estate sector, which in both cases do not respect the communities' property boundaries, encroaching on and fencing off territory belonging to them. In addition, mining activity has caused soil degradation and water pollution, undermining the communities' livelihoods. Faced with this problem, the high Andean pastoral community of Alto Milluni, in collaboration with agents from the academic sector and other organizations, is developing a new economic activity that seeks to generate a transition towards a more sustainable use of the territory. Through community-based tourism, they seek to take advantage of the landscapes, sacred sites, and cultural practices, as well as the vestiges of mining –dams, galleries, and tunnels. This proposal not only transforms the economic practices of community members who were greatly disadvantaged by extractive activities, but also seeks to contribute to the improvement of the Katari Basin and Lake Titicaca.

As the authors of these studies highlight, productive trajectories in these territories leave behind environmental liabilities that undermine the quality of life of those who live there, as a result of processes of territorial accumulation that have created sacrifice territories. It is in these sacrifice territories that local communities use creativity, collective organization, and alliances with academic, governmental, and cooperation sectors to produce alternatives to the extractive models that operated there for decades. Based on the analysis of these cases as processes of popular habitat management, not only is the creation of alliances and alternatives to extractive models revalued, but also the processes of co-production of knowledge between those who know and inhabit the territory and the technicians and external agents who provide other tools. These cases reveal processes of transformation in the relationship with non-human nature. They are examples of transitions from extractive links to more balanced forms of interaction, where the primary goal is not the accumulation of capital, but the search for fairer living conditions for all beings that inhabit the territory.

4.3.2.b The second set addresses issues related to the neoliberalization of nature.

The first case is described by Alejandro Diaz Armas (available at: Lukas et al., 2025) on the process of touristification in the Canary Islands (Spain). During this process, which the author describes in three stages (1960-1973; 1985-1989; 1997-2006), there was an increase in urbanized land area, water demand, energy consumption, waste generation, and territorial transformation, setting in motion processes of commodification of nature. The process of territorial accumulation in the islands, favored by real estate specialization and tourism, met with resistance from local agents, who began to organize collective demonstrations rejecting this development project, which increased in magnitude over the years. The case combines a series of accelerations and decelerations in the transformation of the territory according to disputes between local agents, business groups, and political agents, which in some periods favor transformation and in others the protection of certain natural spaces. Among the achievements of local organizations is the approval of the Protected Natural Areas Law (1987), which included certain natural areas to prevent their

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

modification by port and hotel projects, and, on the other hand, the participatory construction of a program that aims at degrowth from an eco-social perspective. As the author mentions, there is a struggle on the islands to establish different forms of territoriality, where nature is the subject of dispute, on the one hand as a common good to be conserved and on the other as a consumer good to be commodified.

The second case, presented by Carlos Cowan Ros, concerns the commodification of vicuña fiber in the central Andes (available at: Lukas et al., 2025). The commercial exploitation of vicuñas and their derivatives was prohibited from the 1960s to the 1980s under international regulatory frameworks due to the species' risk of extinction. Once this period ended, its sustainable use was authorized, with wild management and under strict animal welfare standards, which allowed the fiber to legally enter the market for the manufacture of luxury garments. The fiber's value chain encompasses a range of actors, from indigenous and rural communities, state agents, and environmental organizations to international textile corporations. These corporations have appropriated 95% of the value generated in the fiber's value chain, while the indigenous and rural communities that live alongside, monitor, and protect the vicuñas only get 5%. To control all links in the value chain, textile corporations deploy different strategies such as purchasing large tracts of land, creating reserves, partnering with local producers, and creating a hybrid species between alpaca and vicuña called paco-vicuña. In Argentina, the limits to the penetration of these corporations are set by a national regulatory framework permeated by the activism of technical and environmental agents who have succeeded in making vicuña a public resource, ensuring that it is managed in the wild, and that local communities are given priority in shearing permits, which are provided by the provincial government.

The cases are different but share a common core: the convergence of political and business actors to develop mechanisms for the neoliberalization of nature, thereby increasing the capacity for capital accumulation. Analyzing these cases from this perspective allows us to highlight and understand the mechanisms by which this occurs and the effects it has. To a greater or lesser extent, we can observe some of the characteristic features of this process described by Castree (2008), such as commodification, which consists of assigning economic value to elements or phenomena that were not previously part of the market; privatization, whereby property rights are assigned to assets that were previously public; des-regulation, which leads to a decline in the involvement of state agencies in the regulation of social life; and re-regulation, which involves transforming the regulatory framework in order to favor the penetration of capital and the processes of commodification and privatization.

In these cases, the process of neoliberalization involves a particular type of advance of capital over nature, since it not only commodifies them, but also occurs under a framework of sustainability. The promotion of ecotourism and nature tourism in the Canary Islands and the sale of “handcrafted” luxury garments by international textile corporations hide behind environmental discourse the reproduction of social inequalities and territorial transformations, giving rise to a phenomenon where the environment is used as a way to legitimize new frontiers of accumulation.

4.3.2.c The third set addresses three cases of resistance to territorial transformations. Although almost all of the cases analyzed so far involve expressions of various forms of resistance, in this section we focus on a few specific cases.

The first case is analyzed by Mónica Marión Cataño and concerns the struggle of the Nasa people in Cauca (Colombia) against the dispossession of their territories (available at: Lukas et al., 2025). The territory inhabited by the Nasa people has historically been affected by a variety of interests, conflicts, uses, and disputes, including: the presence of paramilitary groups and organizations linked to drug and arms trafficking, harassment by extractive companies, the murder of leaders who defend the territory, the cultivation of illicit species, and the voluntary and involuntary recruitment of young people to join armed groups, among others. What the author highlights in her work is how the organization of the people grouped together in the Cauca Regional Indigenous Council (CRIC) resists all these conflicts and attempts to advance extractive activities through a platform of resistance based on the people's Law of Origin and their worldview. This platform forms a set of rules that outlines the strategies and practices of the Nasa people for the defense of their territory, based on respect for the Uma kiwe, or Mother Earth, from which every being obtains what it needs to live, and which is made up of water, plants, animals, humans, and non-humans. As the author points out, the resistance of the Nasa people lies in the search for harmony in their territory and respect for the Uma kiwe, emphasizing that nature has no owners and that its elements are not resources.

Secondly, we will take the case of the conflict over the expansion of the port of San Antonio (Valparaíso, Chile) studied by Ana Laura Galarza (available at: Lukas et al., 2025). In her study, the author contrasts two narratives about the conflict –the official one and other narratives– from the theoretical frameworks of insurgent planning and artistic practices of expanded mediation. In summary, in response to the port expansion project carried out by a state-owned company that would cause the fragmentation of the coastal ecosystem, the dredging of the seabed, pollution from industrial use, and the construction of a border along the entire coast, socio-environmental activism gradually organized and, after several advances and setbacks, the recognition of the ecosystem as the Ojos de Mar Urban Wetland under Law No. 21,202, halting the continuation of the San Antonio Company's project. What is remarkable about this case is the convergence of different strategies of dispute, which on the one hand included judicial strategies using legal and academic arguments to halt the project, and on the other hand, other local lines of sociocultural and artistic action that sought to promote the premise of reconnection with nature from multiple perspectives, such as biocultural, ancestral, spiritual, aesthetic, and emotional.

The last case is the conflict surrounding the Colina River (Colina, Santiago de Chile, Chile) presented by Ignacio Arce and Michael Lukas (available at: Lukas et al., 2025). The authors propose analyzing it as a case of peri-urban extractivism, where the following converge: large-scale mining, which causes pollution; agribusiness, which demands large volumes of water; and the real estate development of gated communities which, in addition to water consumption, built an earthen wall separating them from the rest of the city. In response to the situation caused by the unequal appropriation of common goods and its consequences for the local population, the organization “Investiga Colina” was formed, which resists through three lines of action: projects to declare the Colina River a Protected Wildlife Area (ASP), raising awareness of social inequalities and environmental effects, and promoting

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

environmental education spaces. As the authors propose, the quest to declare the river a protected area is not only a way to resist the projects that are advancing on the territory, but also demonstrates other ways of connecting with the environment, perceiving common goods, and thinking about development.

The cases presented show us three different forms of resistance that stem from the same place: ignoring, contradicting, and fighting against the neoliberal development project. The use of the category of peri-urban extractivism allows us to analyze the specific context of metropolitan peripheries, while the category of expanded mediation artistic practices offers us another form of research, a form of territorial praxis (Horn et al., 2021) that invites us to think differently about the process of knowledge construction, going beyond hegemonic forms and familiar languages. Based on these analyses, we can observe that resistance is not limited to a reactive response to extractive threats, but rather takes the form of a proactive practice capable of generating its own regulatory frameworks –as in the case of the Nasa people– or alternative public policies –such as the Ojos de Mar Wetland and the Colina River Reserve. This resistance is based on plural forms of knowledge expressed and constructed in collective terms, such as the ancestral and cosmological knowledge of the Nasa people or the academic and artistic frameworks in the cases of San Antonio and Colina, which challenge hegemonic knowledge and enable other readings of the link between the elements that make up nature, both human and non-human.

4.3.3 Conclusions

In the words of Walter D. Mignolo (2009), the production of decolonial knowledge has two essential premises: on the one hand, rejecting externally produced descriptions and characterizations of who we are and what we should do from the point of view of “neutral and objective science” and, on the other hand, taking as a starting point that life is more valuable than “material development” imposed by capitalist development rhetoric. To produce decolonial knowledge, the author invites us to practice epistemic disobedience, which involves acknowledging the place of subordination in which all knowledge produced outside the Eurocentric apparatus is located, renouncing the primacy of disciplinary needs over those of our peoples, and generating knowledge around our own “modernities” rather than “modernity.”

As Arturo Escobar (2010) argues, it is impossible to discuss modernity without considering its constitutive relationship with development, coloniality, and decoloniality. Research in terms of “our modernities” therefore involves constructing knowledge from colonial difference –knowledge originating from local experiences shaped by their relationship with Eurocentric modernity. Starting from there, we observe that the different theoretical approaches with which the authors have treated their cases –territorial accumulation, popular and community management of habitat, commodification of nature, peri-urban extractivism, artistic practices of expanded mediation– have given them tools to deepen, to a greater or lesser extent, a situated analysis that collects the voices and experiences of the territories themselves, the generation of local knowledge, and the development projects that are being contested at each point on the map and, therefore, different ways of connecting with non-human nature. Continuing to collect these experiences is urgent for the production of new future horizons that can address the current eco-social crisis.

The analysis of the first set of studies allowed us to understand how collaborative work between actors with different knowledge proposes other ways of connecting with non-human nature based on alternative social production and reproduction projects that challenge the logic of capital accumulation. The second set of studies reveals the need to identify those processes –sometimes invisible or masked by sustainability– that transform the territory by producing new types of commodified nature. The last set of studies explains how practices of resistance can counteract the processes of capital advancement.

Although we can observe the construction of decolonial knowledge in all these works, it is essential to continue working to erase the deep-rooted line that separates society from nature. As Jason Moore (2020, p. 16) describes, “the view of Nature as external is a fundamental condition of capital accumulation,” so epistemologically dismantling that externality is essential to continue building decolonial knowledge.

4.4 Land conflicts and disputes

Carolina Yacamán Ochoa (Universidad Autónoma de Madrid)

4.4.1 Introduction

Soil, a non-renewable resource, constitutes a central factor in capitalist logic and the concentration of global power. As a commodity, soil manifests itself through extractivism, enclosures, and the unequal distribution of land, generating differentiated impacts in the Global South according to ethnic-racial, gender, and class criteria. This distinction is fundamental to understanding socioecological injustice and ecological racism.

The colonial expansion of the 15th century laid the foundations for contemporary structural dependence, which modern metropolises have perpetuated through their ongoing reliance on the resources of the Global South. This dependence is evident today in the persistent dispossession and extractivism occurring across Latin America, the Caribbean, Asia, and Africa. The situation is further aggravated by external debt and the tightening of borders, which expose migrants to systematic violations of human rights, exploitation, and severe health risks. This process operates through the creation of “zones of exception” for Northern elites and “sacrifice zones” in the South, where polluting and toxic activities are concentrated to sustain the capitalist model, deteriorating the quality of life of both human and non-human populations. As Federici (2020) argues, this represents the continuity of a historical process of domination over the means of subsistence.

Land-use change affects one-third of the global surface (Winkler et al., 2021), revealing divergent patterns: forest expansion in the North due to rural abandonment and increasing deforestation in the South driven by agricultural expansion. This trend is directly linked to the North's need to secure strategic resources through the massive acquisition of land, a process known as land grabbing. This phenomenon, central to what Blanc (2024) calls “agropolitics,” intensified after the 2007-2008 commodity crisis, leading to the delocalization of the agri-food system and the expansion of “agricultural frontiers.” Examples include large-scale soybean plantations in Brazil, oil palm cultivation in Indonesia and Malaysia, and banana monocultures in Colombia by large landowners, capitalist farmers, and multinational

corporations. This deterritorialized production pattern generates multiple negative impacts on nature and social well-being, sustained by ecocidal practices.

In this context, the capitalocentric expansion of private property generates deep tensions with the ancestral systems and community-based organizational models of the Global South (Yacamán, 2022). Land enclosures exacerbate inequalities and rural poverty, driving migration. Paradoxically, in the Global North, a significant proportion of migrant women are absorbed by the industrialized horticultural sector, where they face slave-like working conditions and multiple forms of structural violence. They are subjected to specific forms of violence and are frequently excluded from land ownership and decision-making spaces that directly affect them. Research such as the report published by Women's Link (2011) on migrant female farmworkers in Spain documents human rights violations in horticultural plantations, including lack of access to healthcare and justice, exploitation, and the violation of physical and mental integrity.

4.4.2 Case study within the framework of the political and epistemological perspectives of Contested Territories

Recent dynamics of agrarian mobilization in Latin America have transformed the struggle for access to land into the defense of territory, conceived as a common good with the right to use and self-governance by peasant communities. One example of this is the Territorios Campesinos Agroalimentarios (TECAM, Peasant Agri-food Territories), which represent a strategy developed by Colombian peasant communities to counteract the accumulation by dispossession perpetrated by large landowners and foreign capital. These collectively managed territorial figures seek to ensure territorial permanence, food sovereignty, and the conservation of common goods. They constitute a model of social and productive territorial organization that prioritizes agrarian reform programs and rural development, promoting the equitable distribution of productivity, as established by law (Decree 0780).

The consolidation of the TECAM is a direct result of the organizational advancement of peasant movements toward the self-management of territory. They emerge as a counter-hegemonic proposal aimed at preventing the inequitable concentration of rural property and the uneconomic fragmentation of agricultural land. These territorial figures not only partially materialize the goals of the Comprehensive Rural Reform but also align with the broader struggle for the recognition of the peasantry as a political subject of rights (Castillo-Amorocho, W. H., 2020).

A distinctive feature of the TECAM is their holistic approach to agrarian land, which transcends food production and integrates a set of measures to strengthen peasant livelihoods. The Consejo Nacional Campesino (CNA, 2015) defines them as an associative territorial figure designed to guarantee the production and reproduction of peasant communities in their sociocultural, politico-communitarian, and productive-environmental dimensions. Although they establish a private property regime over land, they simultaneously articulate a common-use regime for resources perceived as common goods, such as forests and water sources.

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

According to the study by Nicolás Cely Muñoz (2028), the construction of peasant territoriality by the peasant movement –aimed at halting territorial accumulation– is defined by a set of strategies:

- Peasant Governing Board (Junta de Gobierno Campesino): The highest governing body of the TECAM, materializing the aspiration to establish peasant power in the territory. It is coordinated through representatives elected in municipal assemblies, ensuring gender and generational equity.
- Peasant Guard (Guardia Campesina): Inspired by the Indigenous Guard of the CRIC, this body exercises vigilance and territorial protection. Its concept goes beyond coercive functions; it embodies an attitude of territorial stewardship, summarized in the phrase “We are all the Guard,” which is crucial amid recent territorial and environmental conflicts.
- Caravans of Payment (Caravanas de Pagamento): A ritual similar to ancestral Indigenous practices that seeks to offer retribution and payment to nature for the benefits obtained, reaffirming the community’s connection with nature.
- Sovereignty and Harmonization Mingas (Mingas de Soberanía y Armonización): Gatherings held in places considered sacred, serving both as decision-making spaces for the organizational process and as opportunities for community awareness about the territory.

As can be observed, the strategies of peasant territoriality within the TECAM play a crucial political role in the struggle for territorial sovereignty and the redistribution of power. Both the Caravans of Payment and the Mingas of Sovereignty act as political acts that reaffirm peasant sovereignty in the face of land concentration by external actors such as mining companies, agribusiness corporations, and large landowners.

Likewise, these strategies stand out for their emphasis on self-management in territorial protection and the strengthening of democratic processes. The composition of the assemblies –which include a diversity of local social actors (such as community action boards, water management committees, women’s organizations, youth groups, and environmental associations)– seeks to overcome organizational unilateralism, ensuring inclusion and the legitimacy of collective decision-making.

4.4.3 Conclusions

To mitigate the expulsion and forced displacement of peasant communities from their territories, transformative strategies must necessarily focus on reforming land ownership regulations. It is crucial to address both the concentration of land in the hands of foreign capital and the structural violence inflicted on peasant, Indigenous, and Afro-descendant communities –particularly on peasant women and migrant farmworkers– given the intrinsic causal connection between ownership regimes and exploitation.

For this reason, there is an urgent need for a rigorous analysis of structural variables – especially ethnicity and gender relations– to unravel their role in shaping the social organization of the current production and consumption model. Only through such an

analysis will it be possible to understand and dismantle the mechanisms that perpetuate the present globalized system of production and consumption (Reigada et al., 2017).

Peasant struggles are not limited to resistance; they are active proposals that offer concrete alternatives. Through frameworks such as the Territorios Campesinos Agroalimentarios (TECAM, Peasant Agri-food Territories), communities consolidate themselves as active subjects that, in addition to opposing the expansion of monocultures and agrarian concentration, embody worldviews grounded in the common good. These alternatives seek to strengthen peasant economies and defend nature. However, their protagonism and actions are frequently rendered invisible by the persistence of colonialism, racism, and the prevailing patriarchal culture.

4.5 State Policies in Territorial Accumulation

Carlos Cowan Ros (CEUR- CONICET)

*The state is not the reality
which stands behind the mask of political practice.
It is itself the mask
which prevents our seeing our political practice as it is.
Philip Abrams (1988)*

4.5.1 Regulation and Accumulation

Several authors have emphasized the importance of analyzing economic and regulatory dynamics in a dialectical manner in order to understand the configuration of economic systems and the associated processes of accumulation. In this regard, Karl Polanyi, in *The Great Transformation*, problematized the idea of the free market as a natural state and argued that self-regulated capitalism is, in fact, the result of active state intervention (Polanyi, 1989). More recently, and building upon this debate, Brenner, Peck, and Theodore (2011) proposed understanding the capitalist restructuring that began in the 1970s through a relational analysis between forms of accumulation and forms of regulation. These authors also introduced a distinction between neoliberalism as an ideological doctrine and *actually existing neoliberalism* –or *neoliberalization*– conceived as a spatio-temporal process through which neoliberal principles are materialized in economic and regulatory practices. In this sense, they argue that neoliberalization processes are historically specific, hybrid, incomplete, and uneven, as they are conditioned by particular trajectories, contexts, and resistances (Brenner et al., 2011).

This perspective invites us to move beyond the interpretation of regulations as external forces intended solely to correct or limit the market. On the contrary, it proposes to conceive them as an intrinsic component that shapes the functioning of the market, defines its rules, establishes the actors who participate in it, and determines its outcomes, thereby constituting the core of its transformation and reproduction. Moreover, this approach proves useful in explaining why capitalist restructuring unfolds unevenly at the global level and underscores the need to articulate in the analysis both the logics of territorial accumulation

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

driven by various agents and the regulatory mechanisms institutionalized through public policies across different scales.

This section focuses on the examination of regulatory frameworks. Its purpose is to revisit critical analytical perspectives on the state and public policies in order to identify approaches that allow for the recognition and analysis of the governing devices implemented by state institutions. In particular, it seeks to recover theoretical and methodological perspectives that make it possible to apprehend and analyze the disputes and—often creative—forms of resistance deployed by social actors in their struggles over the definition and implementation of state policies, acknowledging the rationalities, interests, worldviews, and ontologies that are mobilized therein. In analyzing state regulatory mechanisms, it is essential to recognize that these are inscribed within a history marked by the *coloniality of power* and by forms of accumulation that have subordinated local practices and rationalities. Recognizing and incorporating the latter into the disputes over modes of regulation constitutes a way of situating state formations as effects of broader, historical, and ongoing social struggles through which our societies are configured.

4.5.2 The Question of the State: Deviations and the Overcoming of the Liberal Vision

With the constitution of the social sciences, the conceptualization and analysis of the modern state emerged as an object of controversy, giving rise to multiple and often competing perspectives for its study. Georg Friedrich Hegel was among the first liberal philosophers to establish the distinction between the State and civil society, conceptualizing the State as a governing organ that regulates in order to ensure the general welfare of civil society (Molina Jiménez, 1985). This perspective remains one of the most widespread in academic circles, with considerable penetration into the common sense of the population. This latter effect can be understood, in Pierre Bourdieu's terms, as a *doxic complicity* that confers legitimacy upon the idea of the State projected by liberal thought, thereby obscuring the arbitrariness it contains (Bourdieu, 1993).

The liberal perspective was challenged early on by Karl Marx, who emphasized the need to recognize the State as an organ of government serving class interests—more precisely, those of the bourgeoisie. Since then, various critiques of the liberal conception of the State have contributed theoretical and methodological insights that help to avoid analytical distortions and align empirical evidence with the conceptualization of political and social phenomena.

Drawing on the metaphor from the epigraph that opens this section, Philip Abrams, in his 1977 address to the British Sociological Association, called for *de-reifying* the study of the State in analyses of political power. Abandoning the liberal legacy—which (re)presents the State as an entity or even as a concrete agent, autonomous, detached, and hierarchically positioned above the rest of society, endowed with human qualities such as will, power, and agency acting in favor of the general interest—constituted an essential epistemological shift for understanding political organization in modern societies. To overcome this analytical deviation, Abrams proposed studying the State through its symbolic dimension: as an ideological project or artifact (*idea of the State*) that orients the actions of social subjects within the set of political and executive control institutions (*system of the State*), with the purpose of morally legitimizing and regulating the (re)production of social order. From this

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

perspective, reproducing the image of the State as an autonomous and integrated totality not only obscures the heterogeneity, contradictions, and tensions that typically exist among institutions and actors within the state system, but also implies participating in the concealment and naturalization of power exercised through state institutions (Abrams, 2015).

From the 1980s onward, the modern State entered the research agenda of social anthropology, and consequently, the study of the symbolic production of and from the State gained renewed momentum. From an interpretive perspective, and recovering Antonio Gramsci's critique of the separation between State and civil society, scholars began to challenge the idea of the State as a universal category –that is, as possessing regular characteristics independent of society and historical context. One of the most frequently cited pioneering works in this regard is *The Great Arch*, by Philip Corrigan and Derek Sayer (1985). These authors mobilized the notion of *state formation* to study the configuration of the English State as a cultural revolution born of social struggles and productive, among other things, of an illusory community –the *national community* (Corrigan & Sayer, 1985). The State thus came to be interpreted as a *cultural artifact*; no longer viewed as an autonomous entity detached from society, but as a product of social struggles and contestations (Joseph & Nugent, 2002; Sharma & Gupta, 2006; Das & Poole, 2008).

This shift entailed a methodological inversion. Rather than beginning with a predefined definition of the State, the aim became to grasp both the production of materiality (state institutions and policies) and the symbolic dimensions of statehood (the idea of the State and the categories and thought structures produced within state institutions) through the everyday representations and practices of people. From this perspective, the state is constructed both *from within* institutional frameworks –by those who hold positions within them– and *from without*, through the representations and actions directed toward the State by those who do not. In this way, all individuals participate daily in the production of the State, albeit from different positions and with distinct power relations. Among scholars adhering to the interpretive approach, there is broad consensus in privileging ethnography as the preferred method of inquiry.

The role of subaltern social groups in the production of statehood also began to be recognized and valued as a relevant object of study. Joseph and Nugent (2002), for example, focused their analysis on the role of popular classes in the formation of the modern Mexican State after the Revolution of 1910. With the notion of the *margins of the State*, Veena Das and Deborah Poole offered an analytical category to think about “zones of exception” in which state rationality is suspended and permeated by other forms of regulation that emerge from the urgent needs of populations, thereby redefining modes of governing and legislating. The interest in these margins lies in their being spaces of “creativity,” where the (re)making of both the state and the non-state becomes most visible as a result of their encounter (Das & Poole, 2008). These perspectives make it possible to focus analytical attention on the recognition and interpretation of non-Western and/or non-bureaucratic rationalities that permeate state practices –a social phenomenon that has gained increasing relevance in certain state arenas in Latin America.

Traditional analyses of public policy have also been the subject of critique for their epistemological biases. First, the state-centric bias has been problematized, as it restricts

agency to state actors –both in the formulation and implementation of policies– while disregarding the role of non-state agents in these processes. Second, the bureaucratic-normative bias that prevailed in policy studies has been questioned, as it conditioned analysis to the “ought-to-be” of policies. From this perspective, policies were assumed to rest on rational designs aimed at maximizing efficiency and effectiveness in solving problems conceived as objective, following a linear and top-down procedure—from formulation to implementation. As a result, this view confined agency to state officials and hierarchized the potential for influence according to institutional position. While such criteria may guide administrative practice within state agencies, their adoption as analytical premises for the study of public policy constitutes a bias, as they correlate poorly with how empirical phenomena actually unfold. In contrast, the interpretive perspective does not deny the instrumental dimension of public policy but directs analytical attention toward identifying the worldviews that shape its production, as well as the ways in which people recognize, experience, and redefine policy in their everyday practices (Shore & Wright, 1997; Shore, 2010).

4.5.3 Case Studies and the Regulation of Territorial Accumulation

This section draws upon two case studies conducted by members of the network which, despite their theoretical heterogeneity, converge in articulating an interpretive analysis of state policies with the study of territorial accumulation processes. The common thread among these contributions lies in examining how public policies simultaneously enable and constrain specific economic dynamics, thereby shaping differentiated patterns of accumulation and social reproduction.

The conservation and sustainable use of vicuñas (Cowan Ros & Marcos, 2024; Cowan Ros et al., 2022) offers a compelling example in this regard. This species, which was on the brink of extinction in the late 1960s due to the high market value of its fiber, became the focus of a complex, multi-level regulatory system spanning supranational, national, and subnational scales of governance. While there was broad agreement concerning conservation policies, the most significant disputes emerged around the modalities of sustainable use. Two competing management models were at the center of the debate: the captive management model –rooted in livestock production practices and aligned with entrepreneurial economic rationalities– and the wild management model, more consistent with the social reproduction strategies of Andean peasant communities.

Between the 1990s and 2000s, the pertinence of these two models was widely discussed within international agreements and national and subnational legislative frameworks. Through coordinated multi-scalar actions, the proponents of the wild management model succeeded in institutionalizing it within legal and regulatory instruments. Consequently, the sustainable use of vicuñas came to be officially defined as an activity benefiting Andean inhabitants, under state supervision and employing wild management techniques. This regulatory orientation created a barrier for textile corporations seeking to directly engage in vicuña fiber production. Today, the initial phase of production is dominated by members of peasant communities who, through both collective and individual production logics, have incorporated a new source of income into their domestic economies.

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

However, despite its stated objective of benefiting Andean populations, the current regulatory framework does not address value addition along the vicuña fiber value chain. The industrialization and commercialization phases remain controlled by luxury textile corporations that add value outside the Andean region. As a result, peasant fiber-harvesting communities capture only about 3% of the total value added along the chain, revealing an extractivist pattern of accumulation. The analysis of policy referentials regulating the sustainable use of vicuñas has thus made it possible to relate the various regulatory designs to the underlying economic rationalities at play, as well as to identify both the limitations and the potential of current frameworks to promote more equitable outcomes among the actors involved

The case of urban redevelopment and housing policies in Lisbon (Carmo, A. & Estevens, A., 2022) illustrates how the interpretive perspective on public policy enables a more nuanced understanding of state action and its territorial effects than normative or technocratic approaches. Over the past two decades, Lisbon has undergone an intense process of urban transformation driven by the expansion of the tourism economy and the financialization of real estate. Policies promoting “urban revitalization,” “smart cities,” and “creative districts” have been formally presented as instruments for sustainable development and the improvement of urban well-being. However, when analyzed interpretively, these policy frameworks reveal competing rationalities and socio-spatial inequalities that transcend their normative rhetoric.

From a conventional, policy-oriented viewpoint, these programs would be evaluated according to their efficiency in attracting investment, optimizing land use, and improving infrastructure. The interpretive approach, however, shifts the focus toward the meanings, practices, and power relations that constitute urban policy itself. Through ethnographic and discourse-based analysis, researchers from the *Contested Territories Network* have shown how the narratives of “innovation” and “revitalization” operate as symbolic instruments that legitimize processes of dispossession and reconfiguration of everyday life in working-class neighbourhoods. In this context, the State acts not as a neutral regulator but as a heterogeneous assemblage of institutions, actors, and discourses that co-produce new urban orders aligned with financial and touristic logics of accumulation.

The interpretive analysis of Lisbon’s housing policies exposes the coexistence of conflicting rationalities within the state apparatus: on the one hand, the promotion of housing as a market asset; on the other, its framing as a social right and cultural heritage. This tension is not merely institutional but epistemic, as it reflects divergent ontologies of what the city and urban life should be. By tracing how residents, local associations, and municipal officials negotiate these contradictions in everyday governance, the interpretive perspective makes visible the moral and affective dimensions of policy implementation that remain invisible in normative frameworks.

Ultimately, the Lisbon case demonstrates that understanding urban policy through an interpretive lens allows us to see not only how regulations shape markets and territories, but also how they reconfigure social identities, belonging, and the meanings attached to place. In contrast to managerial visions that treat policy as a linear and technical instrument, the interpretive approach reveals it as a contested, historically situated, and meaning-producing practice—one that both reflects and reproduces broader dynamics of territorial accumulation.

4.5.4 Conclusions

This deliverable has consolidated a comprehensive theoretical and empirical reflection on the territorial dynamics of accumulation, interpreted through critical and decolonial lenses. Starting from the premise that capitalist expansion has historically relied on the unequal appropriation of territories and the subordination of peripheral regions, the report reclaims alternative epistemologies capable of exposing the colonial underpinnings of conventional economic and political models. By connecting Marxian, dependency, and decolonial frameworks, it contributes to a renewed understanding of territorial accumulation as a contested and historically situated process shaped by asymmetries of power, knowledge, and value.

The section on *alternative socio-economic rationalities* demonstrated the analytical and political potential of social, solidarity, and popular economies to confront hegemonic models of accumulation. These experiences, grounded in local practices and collective organization, reveal that communities in both the Global South and North can produce viable systems of cooperation, redistribution, and reproduction of life. The comparative cases discussed within the *Contested Territories Network* underscore that such economies are not residual but constitutive of diverse modernities, capable of inspiring policies that privilege life, work, and social reproduction over profit.

In turn, the analysis of *nature's use, appropriation, and regulation* illuminated the ways in which the neoliberalization of nature continues to expand the frontiers of capital through new forms of commodification, while also generating creative processes of resistance. The cases examined –from community-led environmental management to struggles against extractivism– demonstrated that the co-production of knowledge between local actors, scientists, and policymakers can produce alternative modes of relating to non-human natures. These practices, rooted in epistemic disobedience, offer pathways toward ecological justice and a more symmetrical dialogue between knowledges.

The section on *land conflicts* emphasized the centrality of agrarian struggles in redefining the meaning of territory as a common good and space of self-government. The emergence of *Peasant Agro-Food Territories* in Colombia exemplifies how collective governance, gender equity, and ancestral practices can be articulated into new forms of territorial sovereignty. These initiatives materialize decolonial alternatives that challenge land grabbing, racialized exploitation, and the patriarchal organization of production, thereby linking social justice with ecological sustainability.

Finally, the discussion on *state policies and regulation* repositioned the state not as a neutral actor but as a terrain of contestation where multiple rationalities and projects of accumulation interact. By revisiting critical state theory and ethnographic perspectives, the analysis revealed that public policies both enable and constrain accumulation processes, depending on the social forces and epistemologies that inform them. The regulatory cases examined – such as the governance of vicuña fiber– illustrate the tension between market-driven frameworks and community-based approaches to value creation. Altogether, the deliverable demonstrates that advancing a decolonial understanding of territorial accumulation requires not only unveiling the coloniality of power embedded in institutions but also fostering alliances and knowledge co-production that sustain plural and just futures.

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5. SECTION 2: PARTICIPATORY MECHANISMS AND COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE MECHANISMS

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5.1 Introduction

In recent decades, the application and analysis of participatory mechanisms and collaborative knowledge exchange processes have become a central topic of discussion in the social sciences. Various methodological trends, from early proposals such as Participatory Action Research (PAR) to more contemporary approaches to knowledge co-production, have sought to overcome the conventional extractive research model and replace it with more inclusive, holistic and contextually situated research models (Fals Borda, 2001; Norström et al., 2020). These methodologies respond, on the one hand, to the need to generate relevant knowledge in the face of the complex challenges presented by our social, environmental and political reality, but they also seek to raise ethical questions about the asymmetrical power relations between academia and other forms of knowledge.

In community work, participation is conceived as a process of social construction in which individuals increase their capacity for influence by intervening directly in the different phases of projects, taking on an active role in decision-making. This transformative nature of participation strengthens citizen power and consolidates its role in community development. However, although there is consensus at the discursive level on its relevance, in practice there are tensions and limitations that open up the debate about the possibilities and limits of participation in both public management and research.

Democracy, citizenship and pluralism must be understood within the framework of societies traversed by multiple and unequal centres of power. This means recognising the interdependence of problems and actors and overcoming classic models of intervention characterised by their verticality and fragmentation. Instead, inclusive community strategies are required, based on the complexity of the territories and the articulation of local networks (Pastor Seller, 2004).

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

From this perspective, citizen participation cannot be reduced to a formal mechanism for gathering information, but rather constitutes a dynamic and synergistic process of involving actors throughout the research process, articulating diverse knowledge and generating spaces for collective learning, in which professional incorporation in the design and management of participatory devices is key. Based on principles such as plurality, exchange and convergence of interests, these processes represent an opportunity to produce more relevant knowledge in the face of the complexity of the contemporary world (Boavida, 2011; Cockburn, 2019; Norström et al., 2020).

Participation understood as cooperation and integration of knowledge favours not only local development, but also the production of knowledge and the strengthening of social cohesion (Pastor Seller, 2004), by consolidating and/or strengthening the social networks and links that sustain collective action. Indeed, participation is closely linked to sustainable human and social development, constituting a central axis of public policies aimed at inclusion.

Within this framework, the following section systematises and critically analyses how the participatory mechanisms deployed in Contested Territories have contributed, with their achievements and limitations, to generating effective processes of knowledge co-production, and what lessons they offer for the theory and practice of participatory research in a decolonial key. Unlike the literature, which tends to present isolated case studies, this work integrates several methodologies and evaluates them in light of Latin American critical traditions and contemporary frameworks on knowledge co-production. In this way, it seeks to contribute to building a bridge between theory and practice, highlighting both the potential and the limitations of participatory mechanisms for generating effective processes of knowledge co-production, in order to identify conditions, risks and opportunities that guide the design of future collaborative processes.

5.2 Why is it important to develop participatory and collaborative mechanisms?

The study of participatory and collaborative mechanisms is fundamental for academia and society in general, as it involves a broader debate on the forms of knowledge production and the power relations involved. These are not merely instrumental tools, but spaces where divergent conceptions are questioned about who can or cannot produce valid knowledge, under what agenda and considerations, and what characterises knowledge with the potential to influence decision-making for the collective well-being.

Participation cannot be understood solely as a political right, but also as a social practice of building the common good, in which various actors –citizens, social organisations, communities, institutions– are involved in the deliberation, design, implementation and evaluation of the policies that affect them, and/or in the definition of objectives, collection, systematisation and drafting of results in the research of which they are a part. In this sense, participatory mechanisms are a key tool for democratising decision-making processes, opening channels for the recognition of historically excluded knowledge, interests and needs. Palma (1997) emphasises that there can be no genuine participation without redistribution of power and without opening spaces where the capacities of local actors are recognised and articulated with effective opportunities to influence decisions.

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Various theoretical approaches and empirical experiences –participatory budgets, deliberative forums, territorial roundtables and prior consultation policies– demonstrate the potential of these mechanisms to redefine state action from a dialogical, inclusive and pluralistic perspective. Gaventa (1998; 2006) and De Sousa Santos (2002; 2011), among others, have contributed to conceptualising these experiences as forms of empowered participatory governance that articulate democracy, cognitive justice and social transformation. The collaborative development of public policies involves moving beyond vertical models of state planning and committing to more horizontal, polycentric and situated forms of governance.

Undoubtedly, these reflections linked to the field of public policy and development are directly correlated to the field of social research and debates on knowledge production. Participatory and collaborative mechanisms in research not only redefine the relationships between researchers and communities, but also challenge the power dynamics between the global North and South, questioning the epistemic hierarchies inherited from colonialism and paving the way for the co-production of situated knowledge. In this sense, the "theory of the South" constitutes a critique of Eurocentric epistemological perspectives, and the injustices generated in the development of theory (Lawhon & Truelove, 2020; Murrey, 2018; Rosa, 2014; Connell, 2007). Authors such as Boaventura de Sousa Santos (2011) propose looking at the world through "pluriversal" ideas that reveal what has been made invisible in the scientific traditions of the North (Murrey, 2018). The "theory of the South" also calls for not generalising or rigidly separating what corresponds to the North or the South (Murrey, 2018; Watson, 2014), but rather recognising them as diverse spaces. Hence their proposal to seek alternative sources of intellectual authority, respect local particularities, and establish dialogues with the knowledge produced in colonised contexts (Connell, 2007).

Participation in research can reproduce functional logics —instrumental data collection that legitimises external decisions— or, conversely, take on a substantive character when it enables processes of reflection-action that strengthen local capacities, validate alternative knowledge, and generate concrete social transformations.

5.3 Participatory mechanisms are not neutral

Participatory mechanisms are central to the contemporary discussion on democracy, governance and knowledge production. Although participation has gained greater visibility at the heart of various development approaches since the 1990s, its roots date back to debates that began in the 1930s (Cornwall, 2006).

While some of these approaches gradually disappeared, others evolved and were reconfigured around new currents of thought and institutional agendas (Hickey & Mohan, 2004). In this process, the contributions from Latin America by Paulo Freire and Orlando Fals Borda had a major influence.

In Freire's "dialogic pedagogy," knowledge is a social construct, the product of horizontal dialogue between educator and learner (Jaramillo, 2008), a process of mutual learning where the voices of all participants are equally valued. Research is understood as a "committed practice" of co-producing new knowledge between the researcher and the

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

participants in order to promote changes in the social order and move towards a more humanised world, based on the principle of democracy.

During the 1980s and 1990s, multiple developmental methodologies drew on this basis: Participatory Rural Appraisal, Participatory Learning and Action, or sociograms and citizen juries (Francés et al., 2015), which also inspired the emergence of Participatory Action Research (PAR) as a critical response to positivism and technocratic development projects that rendered popular subjects invisible in Latin America, Africa, and Asia (Fals Borda, 1999; Orłowski, 2019).

In the field of planning, this coincided with the emergence of questions about the limitations of the technocratic model, which placed planners as experts bearing objective knowledge, and the possibility of a participatory planning model that would give citizens the opportunity to be part of the planning processes began to be discussed (Theyyan, 2018; Healey, 2006). These proposals sought to displace the expert as the sole bearer of knowledge and recognise the validity of situated, ancestral and experiential knowledge (Connelly, 2015; Hickey & Mohan, 2004; Gaventa, 1998). These arguments were consolidated in a proposal for "collaborative planning," inspired by Habermas and Giddens, which posited deliberation as the core of planning (Forester, 1999; Innes & Booher, 2014; Healey, 1997). According to this approach, the role of the planner had to be transformed: no longer as an expert offering solutions, but as a facilitator of interactive dialogue in which actors negotiate interests, exchange and generate knowledge collectively (Forester, 2006; Healey, 2003).

These participatory approaches, which emerged in various branches of academia, science and development during the 1990s, were widely disseminated and promoted by NGOs, United Nations agencies and, in particular, the World Bank, consolidating participation as a pillar of policies to combat poverty and social exclusion, particularly in the Global South (Van Lindert, 2016; Connelly, 2009; Watson, 2002; Gaventa, 1998).

However, this expansion was accompanied by strong criticism warning that these methodologies, when institutionalised, could reduce participation to a set of techniques for extracting information from 'clients' for technocratic legitimisation purposes (Goldfrank, 2009). Cooke and Kothari (2001) denounced the "tyranny of participation," pointing out that participatory practices promoted as "best practices" could reproduce and reinforce power inequalities. In response, scholars such as Hickey and Mohan (2004) defended the need to reposition participation within broader frameworks of politics and power, highlighting its transformative potential when linked to struggles for social justice and redistribution.

From this more critical perspective, John Gaventa (2006) explored how power relations shape access to, use of, and control over participatory spaces. His well-known "theory of spaces, places and levels of power" analysed when and how participation is possible, real or transformative, distinguishing between spaces created "from above", conquered "from below" or autonomous. Gaventa warned that not all participation is empowering; on the contrary, many mechanisms are co-opted or function as legitimisation of decisions already made.

In this critical vein, the Epistemologies of the South developed by Boaventura de Sousa Santos (2002) questioned hegemonic forms of knowledge and public policy. According to

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

this author, for participation to be effective and emancipatory, it must recognise epistemological plurality and allow for dialogue between different forms of knowledge. Participation should not be limited to listening, but rather to building policies based on the experience, history and rationality of peoples and communities. De Sousa Santos (2002) distinguishes between a representative liberal democracy, centred on institutions and procedures, and a participatory democracy, built on social struggles, popular deliberation and direct action, that is, one that sought to transform the way in which the public sphere is produced.

These critical perspectives agree that participation should be understood as a political, epistemic and cultural right, and warn against the co-optation or symbolic emptying of participation by the state or international organisations when it is reduced to consultative mechanisms without binding power. As Pain & Francis (2003) and Francés et al. (2015) point out, participatory methodologies are not just isolated techniques (such as workshops, group interviews or mapping exercises), but relational processes that seek to generate critical reflection, collective learning and transformative capacities in those who participate.

The evolutionary process of participatory conceptualisations and methodologies, which have moved between functional visions aimed at improving the efficiency of projects and policies under technocratic or neoliberal logics, and substantive visions that seek to enable deliberation, social learning and the construction of citizenship (Ellner, 2013; Goldfrank, 2009), shows that participatory mechanisms are not neutral: they can both reinforce existing power structures and open spaces for questioning them. Their value depends on transcending the merely consultative instrumental level to legitimise decisions already taken, to enable deliberation, social learning and to give citizens the power to transform their environment (Arnstein, 1969).

5.4 From participation to collaboration: collaborative mechanisms for knowledge exchange

Although participatory mechanisms sought to open spaces for inclusion and deliberation, in many cases they failed to generate horizontal processes of joint knowledge construction. In this sense, collaborative mechanisms can be considered a step beyond participation because they do not focus solely on incorporating diverse voices, but on establishing co-production dynamics that articulate knowledge, experiences and capacities under conditions of reciprocity. Collaboration is not the same as mere cooperation (Boavida & Ponte, 2011); while cooperation can reproduce pre-existing hierarchies, collaboration requires negotiation, joint decision-making and mutual learning.

In practice, collaborative mechanisms are deployed in mixed teams between academia and civil society, policy co-design platforms or citizen laboratories. These processes are characterised by uncertainty and the need for trust and dialogue between actors with different backgrounds and languages (Boavida & Ponte, 2011). Trust, together with the recognition of the diversity of contributions, is an indispensable condition for exchanges to be effective and not lead to extractive practices or the subordination of some knowledge to others. In this sense, collaboration introduces a relational emphasis: the effectiveness of processes depends less on institutional frameworks and more on bonds of trust, incremental agreements and collective capacities for action (Cockburn et al., 2019).

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

In the field of sustainability, Norström et al. (2020) propose four principles that guide processes of co-production of quality knowledge: being contextual, pluralistic, oriented towards shared goals, and interactive. These principles imply recognising that there is no single model of collaboration, but rather that it must be situated within the social, political and ecological conditions in which it is embedded. Cockburn et al. (2019) highlight that in contexts of high diversity and conflict, consensual processes are often insufficient or unrealistic. Instead, they propose a pluralistic and relational approach, based on small collective agreements, the building of trust and the strengthening of collaborative capacities through concrete actions. Plurality demands explicit recognition of multiple forms of knowledge –scientific, local, ancestral, technical– and their constant interaction. The common goal-oriented nature of these processes underscores the need for collaborative processes to define collective and shared objectives, while interactivity is expressed in the practice of continuous feedback and iteration.

These conditions connect with a critical and decolonial perspective, in that collaboration does not only mean sharing information. Collaborative mechanisms for knowledge exchange are particularly relevant insofar as they challenge epistemic extractivism and promote the recognition of Southern epistemologies (De Sousa Santos, 2002), the need to redistribute epistemic authority, and the opening of channels so that knowledge produced from the margins can have an impact (Johnson et al., 2025).

In short, collaborative knowledge exchange mechanisms should be understood as iterative, situated and relational processes with the potential to bring together different types of knowledge and actors to produce relevant and contextualised knowledge, while advocating for social and political transformations towards a more just and pluralistic future.

5.4.1 Digital participation platforms

Citizen participation supported by digital technologies has now established itself as a key element of new forms of governance. Digital platforms are online spaces where policy ideas can be proposed, voted on or debated. They not only offer citizens the possibility of expressing opinions and initiatives more directly, but also transform the power relations between institutions and society. However, reports and studies warn that the absence of clear, two-way feedback mechanisms reduces the real scope of this participation in decision-making processes, which in turn weakens its democratic legitimacy (Shin et al., 2024). Huayra Romero & Contreras Rivera (2025) analyse the main findings on digital citizen participation in local governments and show that, although digital platforms have expanded the channels of interaction between citizens and local institutions, their effectiveness is limited by the lack of feedback, low uptake by certain social sectors and gaps in digital skills.

These conclusions are in line with those of Norris (2001), who warns that the incorporation of ICTs into public management does not in itself guarantee greater democracy, but may reproduce existing inequalities. Similarly, Mossberger, Tolbert, and McNeal (2008) point out that digital participation is deeply influenced by socioeconomic factors that can restrict effective inclusion. Thus, the potential of digital environments to positively transform the relationship between the state and society exists only when accompanied by genuine deliberative mechanisms (Chadwick, 2011), as well as the design of institutional processes

that not only channel demands but also guarantee the influence of citizens' voices (Coleman & Shane, 2012).

5.4.2 Participatory and knowledge co-production processes carried out by the Network

The trajectory of Contested Territories demonstrates that participation can take many forms and is supported by a repertoire of tools that seek to make local knowledge visible, promote dialogue between types of knowledge, and facilitate collective decision-making. Likewise, knowledge exchange is conceived as a continuous cycle of production, validation, and feedback of information, in which academia and communities co-produce results and use them to influence local policies and practices.

The classification of the types of participation and collaboration mechanisms presented in this document was developed based on the systematisation carried out in the reports Deliverable 5.1 Other Knowledge Toolkit (Horn et al., 2025) and Deliverable 5.2 Documentation of Community Workshops (Zunino & Paz, 2025), which collect and organise a wide range of participatory experiences developed by the nodes of the Network. The typological proposal therefore arises from the analysis of specific experiences recorded throughout the project, complemented by the authors' track record and critical reflection in other parallel research processes in which similar mechanisms were applied (such as community workshops, collective mapping workshops, community surveys, critical tours of the territory, among others).

Thus, the systematisation presented below combines two sources of validation: on the one hand, the empirical evidence generated in the territory, and on the other, the experience accumulated in action research processes, co-production of knowledge and collaborative practices developed in related contexts. This allows us not only to organise the diversity of participatory mechanisms used in an analytical manner, but also to situate them within a broader field of methodological debates on collaborative research, participatory action research (Fals Borda, 1999; Freire, 1970; Pain & Francis, 2003) and co-production of knowledge in sustainability and urban justice (Norström et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2025).

- *Community workshops*

Community workshops were the most widespread methodological format in the research and knowledge co-production processes of the Contested Territories Network, with at least seventeen documented experiences, including participatory design processes, social mapping, linguistic revitalisation, intergenerational transmission of knowledge, gender and environment workshops, and spaces for the construction of living memories. Their scope was diverse: from the participatory design of urban spaces to intergenerational encounters for linguistic revitalisation or the construction of living memories. Beyond the format, the workshops were configured as platforms for diagnosing common problems, producing situated knowledge, and testing collective solutions, while contributing to building trust and strengthening organisational action. In short, the workshops enabled organisational strengthening, co-creation, and community empowerment.

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

The workshops demonstrated a high capacity to build trust, articulate shared diagnoses and test collective solutions, and thus established themselves as one of the most fertile spaces for collective learning. They enabled frank dialogue between actors with diverse backgrounds, building trust and underpinning local organisational action, becoming true laboratories of social innovation. Their main strength lay in the experience of mutual learning with local communities and actors, consolidating spaces for deliberation and collective action.

Given that the dynamics of participatory workshops often run the risk of being limited to consultation rather than true co-production, the challenge lies in ensuring facilitation that not only promotes speaking out, but also the ability to influence, and in sustaining the processes beyond the specific moment of the workshop. This is the way to address the limitation in terms of sustainability over time, given that community workshops usually depend on external resources and the presence of academic facilitators, which creates risks of discontinuity and loss of organisational dynamics once the research intervention has concluded.

- *Multi-stakeholder meetings and dialogues*

Spaces for encounters between communities, academics, activists, NGOs and local governments to exchange knowledge and build joint agendas, including inter-community encounters, intergenerational encounters, knowledge encounters, South-South dialogues and co-design roundtables. These spaces enabled intercultural and intergenerational transmission and articulation and the revaluation of identity and demonstrated the capacity to bring together heterogeneous actors such as social organisations, universities, indigenous communities and local governments and to translate local experiences into comparative learning with regional or transnational reach.

Thus, these exchange processes transcended the scale of the specific project to feed broader networks of political and epistemic influence; they expanded the scope of local experiences, allowing for the articulation of diverse territorial scales and the establishment of transnational networks. The possibility of translating local struggles into comparative learning was one of the most significant achievements. However, the research experiences developed are undoubtedly insufficient to resolve the structural power asymmetries between the different actors— community organisations, academia, and local governments —which can be reproduced over time and reduce the capacity to sustain the commitments made.

Therefore, although these mechanisms contribute to shared goals related to the democratisation of knowledge and epistemic pluralism, the challenge of promoting longitudinal research processes that allow for continued collaborative action remains.

- *Social cartographies and counter-cartographies*

Social cartographies are a tool for constructing community maps, which are fundamental in urban and rural planning, environmental management, and the implementation of public policies. It can be used in practical or academic experiences, integrating local experiences with external observations to achieve active involvement in territorial construction (Diez Tetamanti, 2014; 2024). The participation of social subjects in the territory in the creation of

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

maps highlights aspects that traditional cartography often omits. The inclusion of local knowledge in collective processes not only contributes to strengthening the organisational power of communities by promoting cooperation and joint action, but also reinforces the sense of belonging by linking collective identity with the construction of common projects (Jiménez, 2019).

Collective mapping was a key tool for highlighting territorial inequalities. Through drawings, sensitive diagrams and insurgent digital maps, communities challenged official narratives and symbolically reappropriated their territories. The use of participatory maps and unconventional territorial representations made it possible to challenge hegemonic narratives about the territory, including cartographies of housing and resettlement, risk and vulnerability maps, map libraries, and others that contributed to making local territorial knowledge visible and legitimate. Insurgent cartographies became highly effective pedagogical and political tools for defending the habitat and creating community agendas capable of challenging hegemonic narratives about territories and highlighting structural inequalities in community planning processes and even in disputes with authorities. However, their replicability is often conditioned by certain limitations: the translation of oral and relational knowledge into a more technical and schematic cartographic language requires specific technical skills that can become a barrier limiting the full participation of some sectors.

In short, social cartographies or counter-cartographies embody epistemic plurality and goal orientation, but they can erode interactivity when translation into technical languages displaces oral and relational voices.

- *Beyond text: sensory methodologies*

Audiovisual, artistic, performative, and sensory methodologies expanded the research repertoire beyond academic text, generating affective memories and intergenerational transmissions from a *sentipensar* (feel-think) approach inspired by Fals Borda (1999). These expressions allowed for plural forms of representing marginalised knowledge and promoted awareness and experiential communication, articulating reason and emotion in the construction of knowledge. They also played a central role in consolidating identities and preserving historical narratives from the communities themselves. These spaces, in addition to documenting, became political instruments for affirming cultural and territorial rights.

Together, these experiences show how participatory research draws on diverse languages –artistic, ritual, sensory, and museum-based– that articulate reason and emotion in the construction of knowledge and allow memory to be both a methodological resource and a strategy of resistance. The incorporation of multiple languages enriched the research processes by allowing for a plural representation of marginalised knowledge, opening up unique possibilities in the production of knowledge. These methods facilitated intergenerational transmission, the construction of affective memories and the sensitisation of broad audiences beyond academia. The most notable opportunity lies in their ability to generate empathy and community cohesion around shared stories.

However, while these mechanisms strengthen pluralism and contextuality by validating non-textual forms of knowledge and recognising memories as evidence and method, they face

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

barriers to institutional validation (academic and policy). At the same time, in many cases, they require resources and technical capabilities that limit their sustainability and replicability in precarious contexts and require clear intellectual property arrangements, shared curation, and institutional sustainability to sustain iteration.

- *Critical territorial field-walks*

Immersion in communities of heterogeneous groups of actors fostered processes of situated understanding, enabling direct dialogue with local actors and practices and opening spaces for collective analysis and reflection on the territory and its socio-economic, cultural, political and environmental dynamics. The walks and critical tours provided first-hand knowledge not only of the perspective of the actors in the territory on the conflicts they face and their proposals for how to solve them, but also constituted mutual learning exercises, in which researchers and communities exchanged points of view in an environment where local narratives took centre stage.

This type of knowledge co-production mechanism has a high impact on those who participate due to the volume and intensity of learning, but it also has high logistical requirements in terms of pre-production time, travel costs, participants' availability, among other challenges. On the other hand, if a clear return to the host communities is not ensured, this type of exercise runs the risk of being perceived as "academic tourism" or as a novel mechanism of epistemic extractivism.

- *Citizen science and collaborative surveys*

These experiences had a concrete impact on the generation of community data of public relevance. They were collaborative or community-led research processes, which validated the research capacity of the social actors themselves and strengthened the opportunity to influence public policy. They demonstrated the possibility of producing data of public interest from a community perspective, strengthening the impact on urban and environmental policies. Examples such as the Tenant Survey demonstrate the potential of these tools to articulate social movements and generate comparative inputs between territories. Their main limitation lies in the methodological complexity of constructing common and comparable instruments, which requires high levels of coordination and resources, which can limit the effective participation of local actors in data collection phases, weakening the emancipatory nature of the process.

"Voces-Territorios" (Voices-Territories), an application produced by researchers from the Contested Territories Network, is a virtual platform that allows participants to collect and link testimonies, voices, photos, videos and texts on urban and rural territorial processes in different parts of the world and locate them on a collective global map from their mobile devices. Its design used a Citizen Science strategy to put it at the service of social movements and organisations, combining various mechanisms of collaborative knowledge co-production: social cartography, critical tours of the territory, multimodal testimonies; knowledge is returned through the collaborative map that is produced.

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

Citizen and collaborative science can align shared goals and increase the legitimacy and salience of co-produced knowledge, but its methodological complexity threatens interactivity if its application remains limited to data collection.

- *University extension programmes*

Other participatory research mechanisms were part of a non-extractive university extension model, such as community legal advocacy or environmental training programmes in watersheds. In these cases, academic actors positioned themselves as a bridge of reciprocity, committing to joint capacity building with communities. These spaces shed light on opportunities for pedagogical innovation and institutional transformation in academia. University extension initiatives marked an effort to overcome the traditional vertical relationship between academia and the community and contributed to building local capacities and redefining the role of the university. However, these processes only achieve their full potential when there is a long-term institutional commitment, which is not always guaranteed. In some cases, the bureaucratic rigidity of universities limits the flexibility needed to sustain horizontal relationships, and dependence on funded projects makes it difficult to consolidate these efforts as permanent practices. This mechanism can activate Norström's four dimensions (contextuality, pluralism, goals, interactivity) when there is long-term commitment and institutional support; otherwise, institutional university extension runs the risk of being perceived as academic welfare rather than a genuine exercise in co-production.

Taken together, the mechanisms analysed show that participation is not limited to specific formats but is sustained by iterative and relational processes in which workshops, cartography, visits, citizen science, meetings and outreach programmes operate as hybrid spaces for encounter, research and action. Although their boundaries overlap, their power depends on their ability to achieve iteration, epistemic pluralism, situated uses and interactivity (Norström et al., 2020). These conditions, rather than technical attributes, are what make the mechanisms true co-production devices, capable of producing valid and socially useful knowledge. Within this framework, the following section examines how these practices engage with global debates on participation, epistemic justice, and sustainability, and what tensions emerge in their implementation.

5.5 Discussion and contributions

The analysis of the participatory and collaborative mechanisms implemented in Contested Territories reveals lessons that transcend the specificity of each device. More than simple methodological techniques, these mechanisms constitute political and epistemic practices that reconfigure the relationships between academia, communities, and social actors, situating themselves at the intersection between knowledge production, community organisation, and public advocacy (Fals Borda, 1999; Freire, 1970; De Sousa Santos, 2002).

The systematisation of workshops and activities shows that participation does not operate as a single method, but as an ecology of interconnected devices that combine encounter, research and action. This praxis confirms that the co-production of knowledge is iterative, plural, collaborative and goal-oriented (Norström et al., 2020), principles that guide current transdisciplinary research. In the case of the Contested Territories Network, this orientation

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

also included the validation of non-textual knowledge (audiovisual, performative, sensory, museum-based) as legitimate evidence, broadening who can speak and how what is said is validated (Pain & Francis, 2003). Such recognition of epistemic diversity embodies a principle of cognitive justice: the form of knowledge –an affective cartography, a living museum, an audiovisual narrative– becomes a constitutive part of its public authority (Boavida & Ponte, 2011).

At the same time, the Contested Territories project emphasised that co-production must generate useful and immediately applicable inputs –data, protocols, agendas, guidelines– not just academic products. The workshop-action-feedback cycles allowed the results to influence community and political agendas, transforming expectations and roles between the university and society. In this sense, co-production produced not only knowledge, but also networks, capacities, and social capital (Fals Borda, 1999).

In what follows, the findings of the different research experiences are discussed in light of global debates on participation, collaboration and knowledge co-production, grouped into contributions (epistemic, methodological, political and organisational) and lessons learned around persistent tensions.

Contributions

The experiences of Contested Territories confirm that co-production gains depth when it recognises epistemic plurality (local, ancestral, experiential, somatic knowledge) and legitimises non-textual forms of representation. The *Otros Saberes Toolkit* systematises methodologies such as knowledge production beyond text, counter-cartography and dialogue of knowledge between multiple actors, which operated as concrete avenues of epistemic validation.

The Network emphasised iteration and useful feedback—maps, guides, memory files—aligning itself with contemporary quality criteria in co-production: contextual, pluralistic, goal-oriented and interactive processes (Norström et al. 2020). It also managed to incorporate explicit agreements on data, authorship, and intellectual property, an aspect highlighted as crucial in international literature for consolidating collective ownership of knowledge (Pain & Francis, 2003).

Several initiatives translated the exchanges into advocacy platforms, strengthening the legitimacy of data produced "from below" and showing how co-production can articulate scales –neighbourhood-region– and transform lived experiences into public agendas.

In addition, longitudinal trust and an "ethic of hospitality and care" (Freire, 1970; De Sousa Santos, 2002) were consolidated as preconditions for sustaining collaboration. In practice, this involved translations, linguistic mediation, schedules sensitive to community rhythms, and logistical support, avoiding participatory fatigue and enabling non-extractive relationships between the university and the territory (Boavida & Ponte, 2011).

While the mechanisms described above demonstrate significant contributions in epistemic, methodological, political, and organisational terms, they also reveal persistent tensions that condition their transformative scope. These tensions do not negate the value of the

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

processes, but they do show the limits and dilemmas faced by all practices of participation and co-production: how to redistribute power in unequal contexts, how to protect shared knowledge, and how to sustain processes that depend on fragile links and scarce resources over time. Below, we present three critical dimensions in which these tensions are most visible and allow us to understand the structural challenges of moving towards substantive co-production.

Asymmetries of power, representation, languages, and security

The power asymmetries observed are not explained solely by the heterogeneity of actors; they are also (re)produced in how it is decided who represents whom, which languages dominate (technical, legal, academic), and which mediations are used (digital platforms and cartographies, reporting formats). This finding directly echoes Gaventa (2006), who shows that participatory spaces –whether created "from above," conquered "from below," or autonomous– are traversed by power relations that determine who can speak, what counts as evidence, and with what effects. Likewise, the transition from oral narratives to maps or technical reports produces epistemic translations where the interpreter(s) concentrate definitional power; De Sousa Santos' (2002) critique of the hierarchies of "what knowledge is valid" helps to read this asymmetry as a problem of epistemic justice. And, in methodological terms, the risk of tokenism –techniques without redistribution of power or decision cycles– appears to be in line with Pain & Francis (2003) and Cooke & Kothari (2001).

On the other hand, the notion of a "safe space" is problematic when, outside the participatory space, hierarchical relationships (labour, clientelist, governmental) persist that induce self-censorship or the risk of reprisals, especially for the most vulnerable. Bergold & Thomas (2012) point out that the ethical and democratic quality of participatory research depends on procedural conditions (informed consent, confidentiality, rules of interaction) and time for care. In Contested Territories, multi-stakeholder dialogues and some territorial visits showed that dissent does not disappear, it is managed.

Moving from a "granted voice" to shared authority involves: (i) rotating/shared representation and prior agreements on the agenda; (ii) epistemic multilingualism, mutual literacy (technical and political) and a combination of formats (oral, graphic, sensory, textual) to decentralise expert language; (iii) co-curation of translation and analysis (maps, reports, audiovisual materials); and (iv) confidentiality/non-retaliation protocols to make the "safe space" practicable even when asymmetries exist outside the participatory forum (Bergold & Thomas, 2012). This design connects with Freire's emphasis on dialogical praxis and the agency of people as subjects of knowledge, not as informants (Freire, 1970; Fals Borda, 1999), and turns epistemic pluralism (Boavida & Ponte, 2011; Norström et al., 2020) into effective redistribution of interpretive power, in line with the IAP's commitment to knowledge as praxis (Freire, 1970; Fals Borda, 1999). Furthermore, this shifts the aspiration for full consensus towards "courageous spaces" where dissent is legitimate and governed, consistent with interactive and contextual co-production (Norström et al., 2020).

Knowledge governance: reciprocity, ownership and right of veto

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

Tensions do not end with the production of results; co-produced materials, whether in the form of maps, audiovisuals, living museums, or memory archives, can be appropriated or reused without recognition. At the same time, non-textual formats –crucial for making marginalised knowledge visible– face barriers to validation in academic and political spheres and attempts to scale up learning can erase local specificities.

Without early agreements on data, authorship, and licensing, there is a risk of appropriation and erosion of trust. Here, recommendations for applied co-production (e.g., co-authorship and community stewardship frameworks) converge with Pain & Francis' (2003) warning about the traceability of evidence. In turn, non-textual formats that broaden inclusion ("beyond text") clash with academic or policy standards that continue to privilege classic metrics and media, forcing us to broaden validity criteria without sacrificing rigour. Finally, the shift from the local to the comparative requires situated transferability: frameworks for comparison with minimum common cores without erasing the specificities of the context (relational approaches in co-production in Norström et al., 2020).

Therefore, it is crucial to have a knowledge governance package (authorship records, open or restricted licences according to agreements, community-custodied repositories and traceability of uses). In terms of validity and scaling, a dual product strategy (one community-oriented and action-oriented; the other technical-academic for formal advocacy) and a situated transferability approach work best: defining minimum comparable cores (common variables/criteria) and contextual annexes that preserve local fidelity. This protects epistemic sovereignty without renouncing dialogue with institutional standards.

Temporalities and sustainability: iteration, invisible burdens and situated transfer

Participatory processes are sustained by relational timescales (trust, mutual learning) that rarely coincide with the timescales of research projects and their funding (deliverables, calls for proposals, budget closures). Evidence from workshops, field visits and outreach programmes show that processes decline when they are limited to one-off events, without feedback or iteration, and the work that makes them possible, becomes invisible and, therefore, unfunded. Furthermore, when interaction is limited to one-off events, participatory fatigue and perceptions of 'academic tourism' arise.

To avoid participatory fatigue and the perception of "academic tourism," the following are necessary: (i) minimum iterative cycles (dialogued diagnosis, co-design, testing, feedback, adjustment, new co-decision), (ii) products for immediate use in the territory (e.g., guides, maps, memory files) in addition to academic outputs, and (iii) dual organisational anchors (community and institutional/academic with explicit responsibilities). At the same time, people-centred practices must be implemented to ensure respect and a commitment to protect all participants: translations and linguistic mediation; schedules and timetables adjusted to community rhythms; coverage of transport, food and care support; non-hierarchical rules for speaking; reviewable informed consent; establishment of moments for verification and feedback of results; and clear agreements on authorship, data and dissemination. These decisions assume that the link between actors is part of the content of the research and not a mere operational procedure, and are aligned with a decolonial reading of collaborative processes proposed by e Sousa Santos (2002) and with the tradition of participatory action research based on the contributions of Paulo Freire and Fals Borda,

Working Paper 3 – Participatory mechanisms, collaborative development of effective knowledge exchange mechanisms and de-colonial social theory

where dialogue, reciprocity and co-responsibility are conditions for producing valid and socially just knowledge, and turns the principles of co-production (Norström et al., 2020) into guarantees of sustainability.

This document, as a whole, seeks to contribute a reflection on the roles in collaborative research processes. The most recent literature refers to the "facilitating researcher" as the one who opens up dialogical processes and enables speech. The analysis and discussion presented here proposes to go one step further: from the "facilitating researcher" to the "reflective team". This means forming interactive groups that share not only data, but also the critical tasks of problematising, translating, deciding and caring for the process. A reflective team distributes epistemic authority, institutionalises the memory of the project, identifies biases, corrects courses and keeps learning cycles alive beyond specific individuals or funding. This transition is probably where the difference between functional participation and substantive co-production comes into play: it is not a matter of facilitating so that "others" can participate, but of reflecting together so that knowledge and its effects are genuinely shared.

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